

CONVEX OPTIMIZATION IN BANACH SPACES

BY

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**IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT FOR THE REQUIREMENT FOR
THE AWARD OF BACHELOR OF SCIENCE (B.Sc.), IN THE
DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, FACULTY OF SCIENCE,
UNIVERSITY OF LAGOS.**

NOVEMBER, 2019

CERTIFICATION

Having supervised the entire project, I certify that **Adedoyin, Jeremiah Damilola** with Matriculation Number **150806028** developed this project, which is to be submitted to the Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science, University of Lagos, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Bachelor of Science in Mathematics.

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this project to the Almighty God who has been gracious to me throughout my undergraduate studies in the University of Lagos, Nigeria.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

My appreciation goes to Almighty God for his unfailing and unending love during my stay in the University of Lagos and his grace to complete this project.

My sincere appreciation goes to my supervisor, Prof. Olaleru Johnson, and my mentor, Hallowed Olaoluwa (Ph.D) for their guidance, supervision, advice and support. God bless my supervisor and mentor abundantly (Amen!!!)

My heartfelt gratitude goes to my father, Mr. Adedoyin Samuel, mother, Mrs. Adedoyin Rachael, my Brother, Israel and my friend, Akinboye Kemi, your prayers made the difference. Dr. Kamiyor Ola, I really want to appreciate your support since year 1 up till now sir. God bless you abundantly sir.

To my General Superintendent, Pastor W. F. Kumuyi, campus pastor, Pastor Oluwatoyin Popoola, My district pastor, Pastor Emmanuel, my group pastors, Pastor Odemona and Pastor Umoru, as well as Bro Seun, God bless you all abundantly for your investment upon my life. It will never be a waste.

All thanks to all my lecturers in the Department of Mathematics, University of Lagos.

Finally, my sincere appreciation goes to all my classmates, friends, fellowship, NAMSAN executives, NMC fellows, roommates and mentees, the likes of Israel, Mercy, Grace, Titi Otis, Orjibra, Bro Imeh, Ramate Dc, Echelon pastor, Samuel(year1, now in 200 level), Android Senator, Adedoyin Faith, just to mention a few being with you guys were memories to keep.

Thanks to everyone that had at one time encouraged me in the completion of this project and during my stay in the University of Lagos.

I thank you all and may God in His infinite mercy reward you richly.

ABSTRACT

Fundamental definitions and theorems of Convexity, Optimization, Banach spaces and Reflexivity are proved majorly in this project work. The Hahn Banach theorem as well as an application of the Frullani's integral are considered in this project work.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Optimization is one of the integral aspects in fields of Mathematics. It has so many applications in Analysis (Real and Functional), Calculus, Differential Equation (Ordinary and Partial), Numerical Analysis etc. Convex Optimization is one of the key areas of Research in Functional Analysis.

Convex Analysis is the calculus of Inequality while convex optimization is its application.

Convex optimization is a subfield of mathematical optimization that studies the problem of minimizing convex functions over convex sets.

"...in fact, the great watershed in optimization isn't between linearity and nonlinearity, but convexity and nonconvexity." - R. Tyrrell Rockafellar, in *SIAM Review*, 1993

A *convex optimization problem* is a problem where all of the constraints are convex functions, and the objective is a convex function if minimizing, or a concave function if maximizing.

The story of Convex optimization began only some seventy-three years ago. Before the 1940s there were very few papers devoted to the form of inequalities. Of these, the most significant are the paper by Fourier and a paper by Vallee-potissin (1911). Since that time, large numbers of papers have been devoted to this subject. A great many of them deal with convex problems.

The earliest nontrivial problems involving constraints in the form of inequalities appeared in a paper by L.V. Kantorovich.

The vigorous development of convex optimization in a wider sense, began in 1947 in the United States. [The Evolution of methods of convex optimization by V.M. Tikhomirov and edited by Abe Shenitzer]

The aim of this project is to study convex optimization in Banach Spaces using some existing and investing new methods (alongside with the condition(s) for use). Their applications as well to real life problem would also be looked into.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Meaning of Convexity

Definition 1.1.1 (Convex Set): Let X be a Real linear space and $A \subset X$. The set A is called **Convex** if for each $x_1, x_2 \in A$ and for each $t \in [0,1]$, we have $tx_1 + (1 - t)x_2 \in A$.

Diagram of a Convex Set.

For example, Consider the set of closed unit sphere denoted by $S_1(x)$ and defined by $S_1(x) = \{x: \|x\| \leq 1\}$, then $S_1(x)$ is a convex set

Proof: let $x, y \in S_1(x)$. hence $\|x\| \leq 1, \|y\| \leq 1$ and $t \in [0,1]$.

so $\|tx + (1 - t)y\| \leq |t|\|x\| + |1 - t|\|y\| \leq |t| + |1 - t| \leq t + 1 - t = 1$.

Thus, $S_1(x)$ is a convex set.

Definition 1.1.2 (Convex Function): Let X be a real vector space and $B \subset X$. Let $f: B \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ be a map. Then f is said to be **convex** if:

a) B is a convex set;

b) $\forall t \in [0,1]$ and for each $x_1, x_2 \in B$, we have

$$f(tx_1 + (1 - t)x_2) \leq tf(x_1) + (1 - t)f(x_2).$$

Remark: if K is a non-empty Convex Set of a linear space X and $f: K \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ is convex, then the extension \hat{f} of the function f to the whole X and by $+\infty$, that is

$$\hat{f}(x) = \begin{cases} f(x) & \text{if } x \in K \\ +\infty & \text{if } x \in X \setminus K \end{cases} \text{ is also convex.}$$

Furthermore, $\inf_K f = \inf_X \hat{f}$.

Graph of a convex function

For example, define $f(x) = |x|$ then f is convex.

Proof: let $t \in [0,1]$ and $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$.

$$\begin{aligned} f(tx + (1-t)y) &= |tx + (1-t)y| \leq |tx| + |(1-t)y| = t|x| + (1-t)|y| \\ &= tf(x) + (1-t)f(y) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, f is convex.

Remark:

i. f is **concave** if:

a). B is a convex set;

b). $\forall t \in [0,1]$ and for each $x_1, x_2 \in B$, we have

$$f(tx_1 + (1-t)x_2) \geq tf(x_1) + (1-t)f(x_2).$$

ii. f is **proper** if there exists at least one $x_0 \in B$ such that $f(x_0) \neq +\infty$.

Remark: f is convex if and only if $(-f)$ is concave, and vice versa.

Graph of both Convex and Concave Function.

Definition 1.1.3 (Banach Space): Let X be a non-empty linear (vector) space over a field K . Define the **norm** denoted by $\|\cdot\|$ as $\|\cdot\|: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfying the following properties. Let $x, y \in X$

a) $\|x\| \geq 0$

b) $\|x\| = 0$ iff $x = 0$

c) $\|\lambda x\| = |\lambda|\|x\|$ where λ is scalar

d) $\|x + y\| \leq \|x\| + \|y\|$

Thus, the pair $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ is called a **normed linear space**. If X is **complete** (i.e every Cauchy sequence in X converges to a point in X) then $(X, \|\cdot\|)$ is called **Complete Normed Space or Banach Space**.

For example, the set of all continuous real-valued functions on $[0,1]$ and $\|f\| = \int_0^1 |f(x)|dx$ is a Banach Space.

Proof: Let \mathcal{C} denote the set all continuous real-valued functions on $[0,1]$ with the norm $\|f\| = \int_0^1 |f(x)|dx$.

Let $f(x), g(x) \in \mathcal{C}$

1. $|f(x)| \geq 0 \Rightarrow \int_0^1 |f(x)|dx \geq 0 \Rightarrow \|f\| \geq 0$

2. Let $\|f\| = 0 \Leftrightarrow \int_0^1 |f(x)|dx = 0 \Leftrightarrow \int |f(x)|dx = c \Leftrightarrow |f(x)| = 0 \Leftrightarrow f(x) = 0$. Here c is a scalar.

3. $\|\alpha f\| = \int_0^1 |\alpha f(x)|dx = \int_0^1 |\alpha| |f(x)|dx = |\alpha| \int_0^1 |f(x)|dx = |\alpha| \|f\|$.

4. $\|f + g\| = \int_0^1 |f(x) + g(x)|dx \leq \int_0^1 |f(x)|dx + \int_0^1 |g(x)|dx = \|f\| + \|g\|$.

5. \mathbb{R} is complete.

Thus, \mathcal{C} is a Banach Space.

In this paper, we will study some already established concepts and theorems on Convexity and Optimization.

1.2 Aims of the Study

Optimization is an intrinsic concept especially while dealing with the minimum and maximum problems, which is a typical real-world problem.

This research work gives a progressive discussion of the condition for convexity, optimization and reflexivity in Banach Spaces alongside with important theorems attached to it. The research work also aims at supplying proofs to some of the theorems and applying the frullani's integral to obtaining the solution to an area problem in this work.

Finally, in this research work, we will see the capital role of some fundamental concepts.

1.3 Significance of Study

To the best of the author's knowledge, this will be the first time there is an application of the frullani's integral to convex optimization.

1.4 Definition of Terms

Here is some definition that will be needed during the course of this Research work.

Definition 1.4.1 (Continuity): A function $f: D \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be continuous at $x_0 \in D$ if $\forall \varepsilon > 0 \exists \delta > 0: |f(x) - f(x_0)| < \varepsilon$ whenever $|x - x_0| < \delta$.

If f is continuous for all $x_0 \in D$, then f is said to be continuous in D .

Definition 1.4.2 (Lower Semi-continuous l.s.c): Consider a function $f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and a point $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}$.

The function f is said to be lower (resp. upper) semi-continuous at the point x_0 if

$$f(x_0) \leq \liminf_{x \rightarrow x_0} f(x) \left(\text{resp. } f(x_0) \geq \limsup_{x \rightarrow x_0} f(x) \right).$$

The definition can be easily extended to functions defined on subdomains of \mathbb{R} and taking values in the extended real line $[-\infty, \infty]$ If a function is lower (resp. upper) semicontinuous at every point of its domain of definition, then it is simply called a *lower (resp. upper) semi-continuous function*.

Remark: A function f is said to be upper semi-continuous iff $-f$ is lower semi-continuous.

For example, the floor function $f(x) = \lfloor x \rfloor$ which returns the greatest integer less than or equal to a given real number x , is everywhere upper semi-continuous. Similarly, the ceiling function $f(x) = \lceil x \rceil$ is lower semi-continuous.

An upper and a lower semi-continuous function respectively. The solid blue dot indicates $f(x_0)$.

Proposition 1.4.3: f is continuous if and only if it is both upper and lower semi-continuous.

Proof: suppose f is continuous then $\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \inf f(x) = \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \sup f(x) = \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} f(x) = f(x_0)$ for all x_0 .

Therefore, f is both upper and lower semi-continuous.

Conversely, $\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \sup f(x) \leq f(x_0) \leq \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \inf f(x)$. We know that $\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \inf f(x) \leq \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \sup f(x)$.

Therefore, it implies that $\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \sup f(x) = f(x_0) = \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \inf f(x)$ and hence $\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} f(x) = f(x_0)$ for all x_0 and f is continuous.

Definition 1.4.4 (Hilbert Space): Let X be a non-empty linear (vector) space over a scalar field K .

Define the **inner product** denoted by $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ as $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle: X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfying the following properties.

Let $x, y, z \in X$

- a) $\langle x, x \rangle \geq 0$
- b) $\langle x, x \rangle = 0$ iff $x = 0$
- c) $\langle x, y \rangle = \overline{\langle y, x \rangle}$
- d) $\langle ax + by, z \rangle = a\langle x, z \rangle + b\langle y, z \rangle$ where a, b are scalars.

Thus, the pair $(X, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$ is called an **inner product space**. If X is **complete** (i.e. every Cauchy sequence in X converges to a point in X) then $(X, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$ is called **Complete inner product Space or Hilbert Space**.

Definition 1.4.5 (Orthogonal sequence in a Hilbert space): Let X be a Hilbert space. The sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is called an orthonormal sequence if $\langle x_n, x_m \rangle = 0$ for $n \neq m$ and $\langle x_n, x_n \rangle = \|x_n\|^2 = 1$.

Definition 1.4.6 (Dual): Let X be a non-empty normed linear space and define $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfying the following properties below:

- a. f is linear
- b. f is continuous and scalar valued
- c. f is proper.

The set of all such function defined above is called the **Dual** of X and it is denoted by X^* .

Definition 1.4.7 (Reflexive Space): Let X be a non-empty normed linear space and X^* be the dual of X . Let $f: X^* \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, then the **Dual** of X^* (also called the **Bidual** of X) will also be given as X^{**} .

If $X^{**} = X$, then X is called a **Reflexive Space**.

For example, The **Hilbert Space (Complete Inner product Space) H** is a **Reflexive Space**.

Definition 1.4.8 (Topological Space): Let X be a non-empty set and $T = \{O_\alpha | O_\alpha \subset X, \alpha \in I \text{ (indexing set)}\}$ be a collection of open subsets of X . (X, T) is said to be a **Topological Space** if the following are satisfied.

- $\emptyset, X \in T$
- $\bigcup_{\alpha \in I} O_\alpha \in T$
- $\bigcap_{\alpha=1}^n O_\alpha \in T$

Definition 1.4.9 (Neighborhood): Let (X, T) be a Topological Space, and let $x \in X$. A neighborhood of x is a subset of V of X that contains an open set U containing x . i.e. $x \in U \subseteq V$.

Definition 1.4.10 (Convergence of a sequence): Let (X, T) be a Topological Space. A sequence of points $(x_n) \subset X$ is said to converge to a point $x \in X$ if for every open neighborhood B of $x \in X$ there exists an $N \in \mathbb{N}$ such that if $n \geq N$ then $x_n \in B$.

Definition 1.4.11 (Hausdorff Space): Let (X, T) be a Topological Space. (X, T) will be an **Hausdorff Space** if for any $x \neq y$ where $x, y \in X$, there exist the open sets O_x, O_y such that $x \in O_x, y \in O_y$ and $O_x \cap O_y = \emptyset$.

Definition 1.4.12 (Neighborhood Base): Let (X, T) be a Topological Space. Let $x \in X$ and B be a set of neighborhoods of x , B is a **neighborhood basis** at x if and only if for each neighborhood N of x , $\exists M \in B$ such that $M \subseteq N$.

For example, the discrete topology on a set X , the collection of all singleton subsets is a base, and the singleton $\{x\}$ is a local base at x .

Definition 1.4.13 (Hyperplane): Let E be a normed linear space,

- a) A **hyperplane** H in E is simply any set of the form $H := \{x \in E : f(x) = \alpha\}$ where f is a linear functional on E and $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$
- b) Let $A, B \subset E$. We say that the hyperplane H of equation $\{x \in E : f(x) = \alpha\}$ **separate** A and B in the general sense if $f(x) \leq \alpha \forall x \in A$ and $f(x) \geq \alpha \forall x \in B$, and we say that it **separate** A and B in the strict sense if $\exists \epsilon > 0$ such that $f(x) \leq \alpha - \epsilon \forall x \in A$ and $f(x) \geq \alpha + \epsilon \forall x \in B$.

Definition 1.4.14 (Isometry): Let X, Y be metric spaces with metric d_1, d_2 respectively and $f: X \rightarrow Y$ and onto. f is said to be an **isometry** if $d_1(x, y) = d_2(f(x), f(y)) \forall x, y \in X$.

Remark 1.4.15: f is continuous (Indeed since f is isometry, we just let $\delta = \epsilon$, it then follows from the $\epsilon - \delta$ argument of continuity that f is continuous).

Definition 1.4.16 (Defining norm on the space of continuous (bounded) linear function on X (normed linear space): The following are equivalent definition of the norm

- a) $\|f\| = \sup \{k : \|f(x)\| \leq k\|x\|\}$

$$\text{b) } \|f\| = \sup \{\|f(x)\|: \|x\| \leq 1\}$$

$$\text{c) } \|f\| = \sup \{\|f(x)\|: \|x\| = 1\}$$

$$\text{d) } \|f\| = \sup_{x \neq 0} \frac{\|f(x)\|}{\|x\|}$$

Definition 1.4.17 (Frullani Integrals): The table of integrals contains many evaluations of the form

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{f(ax) - f(bx)}{x} dx = [f(0) - f(\infty)] \ln\left(\frac{b}{a}\right)$$

Expressions of this type are called Frullani integrals.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

The story of Convex optimization began only some seventy-three years ago. Before the 1940s there were very few papers devoted to the form of inequalities. Of these, the most significant are the paper by Fourier and a paper by Vallee-potissin (1911). Since that time, large numbers of papers have been devoted to this subject. A great many of them deal with convex problems.

The earliest nontrivial problems involving constraints in the form of inequalities appeared in a paper by L.V. Kantorovich.

The vigorous development of convex optimization in a wider sense, began in 1947 in the United States. [The Evolution of methods of convex optimization by V.M. Tikhomirov and edited by Abe Shenitzer in 1996].

Karthik Sridharan and Ambuj Tewari wrote on Convex Games in Banach Spaces. They study the shortcomings of an online learner playing a multi-round game in a Banach space B against an adversary that plays a convex function at each round. Their results connect online convex learning to the study of the geometry of Banach spaces. They also show that appropriate modifications of the Mirror Descent algorithm from convex optimization can be used to achieve the regret upper bounds. Finally, we provide a version of Mirror Descent that adapts to the changing exponent of uniform convexity of the adversary's functions.

M.S.S. Ali in 2004 also wrote on Descent Methods for Convex Optimization problems in Banach Spaces. This was revised in 2005.

Greedy algorithms which use only function evaluations are applied to convex optimization in a general Banach space X . Along with algorithms that use exact evaluations, algorithms with approximate evaluations was treated by V.N. Temlyakov in 2012 when he wrote on Greedy Approximation in Convex Optimization. A priori upper bounds for the convergence rate of the proposed algorithms was given in his work. Later in 2014, he wrote another paper on Convex Optimization in Banach Spaces with R.A. Devore.

Juan Peypouquet in 2014 intended to guide graduate students and researchers who wish to get acquainted with the main theoretical and practical tools for the numerical minimization of

convex functions on Hilbert spaces. Juan Peypouquet therefore wrote Convex Optimization in Normed Spaces.

Sanjoy K. Mitter wrote the paper Convex Optimization in Infinite Dimensional Spaces. The summary of his writing is thus copied here “The duality approach to solving convex optimization problems is studied in detail using tools in convex analysis and the theory of conjugate functions. Conditions for the duality formalism to hold are developed which require that the optimal value of the original problem vary continuously with respect to perturbations in the constraints only along feasible directions; this is sufficient to imply existence for the dual problem and no duality gap. These conditions are also posed as certain local compactness requirements on the dual feasibility set, based on a characterization of locally compact convex sets in locally convex spaces in terms of nonempty relative interiors of the corresponding polar sets. The duality theory and related convex analysis developed here have applications in the study of Bellman-Hamilton Jacobi equations and Optimal Transportation problems.”

V.N. Temlyakov in 2015 wrote on Greedy Approximation in Convex Optimization constructive approximation. He also released another paper in October 2018 titled “Greedy Approximation in Convex Optimization constructive approximation.” The abstract is given now “He study sparse approximate solutions to convex optimization problems. It is known that in many engineering applications researchers are interested in an approximate solution of an optimization problem as a linear combination of elements from a given system of elements. There is an increasing interest in building such sparse approximate solutions using different greedy-type algorithms. The problem of approximation of a given element of a Banach space by linear combinations of elements from a given system (dictionary) is well studied in nonlinear approximation theory. At a first glance the settings of approximation and optimization problems are very different. In the approximation problem an element is given and our task is to find a sparse approximation of it. In optimization theory an energy function is given and we should find an approximate sparse solution to the minimization problem. It turns out that the same technique can be used for solving both problems. He shows how the technique developed in nonlinear approximation theory, in particular, the greedy approximation technique can be adjusted for finding a sparse solution”.

This project will major on fundamentals concept as well as rigorous background of optimization particularly convex optimization in Banach space.

CHAPTER THREE

REFLEXIVE SPACES

3.0 The Hahn Banach Theorem.

Definition 3.0.1 (Gauge): Let E be a normed linear space and $M \subset E$ be an open, convex set with $0 \in M$. $\forall x \in E$, define $p(x) := \inf\{\alpha > 0: \alpha^{-1}(x) \in M\}$. Then p is called a **gauge** of M .

We now state without proof the following lemma.

Lemma 3.0.2: The gauge of M satisfies the following conditions:

- I) $p(\lambda x) = \lambda p(x) \forall x \in E, \lambda > 0$;
- II) $\exists K > 0 : 0 \leq p(x) \leq K\|x\| \forall x \in E$;
- III) $M = \{x \in E: p(x) < 1\}$;
- IV) $p(x + y) \leq p(x) + p(y) \forall x, y \in E$.

Lemma 3.0.3: Let $U \subset E$ be open, convex and nonempty and let $x_0 \in E, x_0 \notin U$. Then there exists $F \in E^*$ such that $F(x) < F(x_0)$ for all $x \in U$. (In particular, the hyperplane of equation $[F = F(x_0)]$ separate $\{x_0\}$ and U in the general sense.

Proof: By translation we may assume that $0 \in U$ (with loss of generality). Introduce the gauge of U denoted by p . Consider the subspace M of E generated by x_0 , i.e., $M = \{x: x = \lambda x_0: \lambda \in \mathbb{R}\}$.

Define $f: M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by $f(x) \equiv f(\lambda x_0) = \lambda$. Then,

- a) f is a linear functional on M ;
- b) $f(x) \leq p(x) \forall x \in M$.

By theorem 3.0.1 below, there exists a linear functional $F: E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ extending f and such that $F(x) \leq p(x) \forall x \in E$. In particular, taking $\lambda = 1$, we have, since $x_0 \in M$, $F(x_0) = f(x_0) = 1$. Furthermore, from II of the above lemma, F is continuous and from III of the above lemma $\forall x \in U F(x) \leq p(x) < 1 = F(x_0)$. The proof is complete.

We state without proof the analytic form of the Hahn Banach theorem.

Theorem 3.0.4 (Hahn Banach theorem, Analytic form): Let M be a subspace of a real linear space, V ; $p: V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a sublinear functional on V , and $f: M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ a linear functional on M such that

$f(x) \leq p(x) \forall x \in M$. Then,

- a) there exists a linear functional F defined on V which is an extension of f ;
- b) $F(x) \leq p(x)$ for all $x \in V$.

We now state and prove the geometry form of the Hahn Banach theorem.

Theorem 3.0.5 (Hahn Banach theorem, first geometry form): Let E be a normed linear space and $A, B \subset E$ be two convex sets, non-empty and disjoint. Suppose that A is open. Then there exists a closed hyperplane that separate A and B in the general sense.

Proof: we shall be applying lemma 3.0.3. Put $U := A - B = \{a - b: a \in A, b \in B\}$. Then,

- a) U is nonempty;
- b) $0 \notin U$;
- c) U is open;
- d) U is convex.

By lemma 3.0.3 $\exists f \in E^*$ such that $f(z) < f(0) = 0 \forall z \in U$.

But $z \in U \Rightarrow z = x - y$ for $x \in A, y \in B$. Thus, $f(z) < 0 \Rightarrow f(x - y) < 0 \Rightarrow f(x) < f(y) \forall x \in A, y \in B$.

Choose r such that $\sup_{x \in A} f(x) \leq r \leq \inf_{y \in B} f(y)$, and so the hyperplane H of equation $[f = r]$ separates A and B in the general sense.

Theorem 3.0.6 (Hahn Banach theorem, second geometry form): Let E be a normed linear space and $A, B \subset E$ be two convex sets, nonempty and disjoint. Suppose that A is closed and B is compact, then there exists a closed hyperplane that separate A and B .

Proof: For $\epsilon > 0$, set

$$A_\epsilon := A + B_\epsilon(0), B_\epsilon := B + B_\epsilon(0)$$

Then,

- i) A_ϵ and B_ϵ are convex, nonempty, and open;
- ii) $A_\epsilon \cap B_\epsilon = \emptyset$ for sufficiently small $\epsilon > 0$.

By theorem 3.0.5, there exists a closed hyperplane of equation $[f = \alpha]$ which separates A_ϵ and B_ϵ in the general sense, so that we have $f(x + \epsilon z) \leq \alpha \leq f(y + \epsilon z) \forall x \in A, y \in B, z \in B(0,1)$. Consequently, we obtain the above inequality that $f(x) + \epsilon \|f\| \leq \alpha \leq f(y) - \epsilon \|f\| \forall x \in A, y \in B$. Since $\|f\| \neq 0$, this implies that A and B are separated in the strict sense by the hyperplane of equation $[f = \alpha]$. This complete the proof.

We proceed to state without proof the closed graph theorem.

Definition 3.0.7 (Closed graph): Let X and Y be normed linear spaces and $T: X \rightarrow Y$ be any map. Then, the graph of T denoted by $G(T)$, is defined by $G(T) := \{(x, Tx) : x \in X\}$.

Observe that $G(T)$ is a subset of $X \times Y$ and that $(x, y) \in G(T)$ if and only if $Tx = y$.

Theorem 3.0.8 (Closed graph theorem): Let X and Y be real Banach spaces. Let

- i) $T: X \rightarrow Y$ be a linear map;
- ii) The graph of T , $G(T)$, be closed.

Then, T is continuous.

3.1 Weak and *Weak** Topologies.

Notion from General Topology.

Let I be an arbitrary index set, E be a set and let $\{Y_i\}_{i \in I}$ be a family of topological spaces. For each $i \in I$ we shall associate a map,

$$\phi_i: E \rightarrow Y_i$$

Observe that if E is endowed with the *discrete topology* (i.e the topology in which every subset of E is open) then each ϕ_i is continuous. Indeed, if we take any open set in $B_i \subset Y_i$ then $\phi_i^{-1}(B_i) \subset E$ which will be open because every subset of E is open. Thus, the ϕ_i 's are continuous.

Now, we have proved that we can endow E with the discrete topology which will make the ϕ_i 's continuous. We now wish to find how to endow E with a smallest topology such that the map

$\phi_i \forall i \in I$ are continuous. We now construct a topology τ on E with minimum open sets which makes $\{\phi_i\}_{i \in I}$ continuous.

Let $\omega_i \in Y_i$ be open, if we are able to find the topology τ , then $\phi_i^{-1}(\omega_i)$ is necessarily in the topology τ , because ϕ_i will be already continuous after obtaining τ . When ω_i are open in Y_i , $i \in I$, the sets $\phi_i^{-1}(\omega_i)$ constitute a family of subsets of E which are necessarily in the topology τ . Denote this family by $U = \{U_i\}_{i \in I}$ where $U_i = \phi_i^{-1}(\omega_i)$ for some $i \in I$. Thus, the topology we are looking for must necessarily contain inverse images (under ϕ_i) of all open subsets of Y_i 's

The Construction of τ .

We first of all find the finite intersections of members of U . in this way, we obtain a family $\Phi = \{\phi_i\}_{i \in I}$ of subsets of E closed under finite intersections. We then consider the family of arbitrary unions of members of Φ . This family is clearly closed under arbitrary unions. We shall denote it by τ .

3.2 The Weak Topology.

Let E be a Banach Space and $f: E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. For each $f \in E^*$ (the dual of E), we associate a map $\phi_f: E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by $\phi_f(x) = \langle f, x \rangle = f(x)$ for all $x \in E$. As f ranges over E^* , we obtain a family $\{\phi_f\}_{f \in E^*}$ on maps of E into \mathbb{R} .

Definition 3.2.1: The weak topology on E (denoted by ω) is the smallest topology on E which makes the maps ϕ_f continuous. We denote weak convergence by \rightarrow

Proposition 3.2.2: Let (E, ω) denote a Banach Space endowed with the topology. Then $x_n \rightarrow x$ in (E, ω) iff $\phi_f(x_n) \rightarrow \phi_f(x)$.

Proof: Given $\phi_f: E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be endowed with the weak topology, then ϕ_f is continuous i.e if $x_n \rightarrow x$ then $\phi_f(x_n) \rightarrow \phi_f(x)$.

Conversely, let $\phi_f(x_n) \rightarrow \phi_f(x)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. We want to prove that $x_n \rightarrow x$. So, let U be a neighborhood of x . We want to produce an N such that for all $n \geq N$, we have $x_n \in U$. Since E is endowed with the topology τ . Suppose that U is of the form $U = \bigcap_{i \in J} \phi_i^{-1}(V_i)$, $J \subset I$. J finite, where V_i is open in Y_i and contain $\phi_i(x)$. For each $i \in J$. Since $\phi_i(x_n) \rightarrow \phi_i(x)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$, there exist an integer N_i such that for all $n \geq N_i$. $\phi_i(x_n) \in V_i$.

Let $\max_{i \in J} N_i$. We then have for all $n \geq N_i$, and for $i \in J$, $\phi_i(x_n) \in V_i$. This implies $x_n \in \bigcap_{i \in J} \phi_i^{-1}(V_i) = U$. Since U was arbitrary, it follows that $x_n \rightarrow x$. The proof is complete.

Proposition 3.2.3: The weak topology is Hausdorff.

Proof: we prove this using the Hahn Banach theorem.

Let $x_1, x_2 \in E, x_1 \neq x_2$. We shall construct U_1, U_2 open in the weak topology such that $x_1 \in U_1, x_2 \in U_2$ and $U_1 \cap U_2 = \emptyset$. Observe that $x_1 \neq x_2$ implies that the sets $\{x_1\}$ and $\{x_2\}$ are disjoint. Clearly, these two sets are also convex (if we take $t \in [0,1]$, we have $tx_1 + (1-t)x_1 \in \{x_1\}$), closed and non-empty. Furthermore, they are compact. By the Hahn Banach theorem, there exist a closed hyperplane which separate $\{x_1\}$ and $\{x_2\}$. Hence $\exists f \in E^*$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $f(x_1) < \alpha < f(x_2)$.

We now set $U_1 = \{x \in E: f(x) < \alpha\} = \phi_f^{-1}\{(-\infty, \alpha)\}$, and $U_2 = \{x \in E: f(x) > \alpha\} = \phi_f^{-1}\{(\alpha, \infty)\}$. Clearly, U_1, U_2 are open in the weak topology, $x_1 \in U_1, x_2 \in U_2$ and $U_1 \cap U_2 = \emptyset$.

Proposition 3.2.4: let $\{x_n\}$ be a sequence in E . we have the following results.

- $x_n \rightarrow x \Leftrightarrow f(x_n) \rightarrow f(x)$ for each $f \in E^*$;
- $x_n \rightarrow x \Rightarrow x_n \rightarrow x$;
- $x_n \rightarrow x \Rightarrow \{x_n\}$ is bounded and $\|x\| \leq \liminf \|x_n\|$
- $x_n \rightarrow x$ (in E), $f_n \rightarrow f$ (in E^*) $\Rightarrow f_n(x_n) \rightarrow f(x)$ (in \mathbb{R})

Proof:

- The proof is same as proposition 3.2.2
- Given $x_n \rightarrow x$, we want to prove that $x_n \rightarrow x$. From (a) above it suffice to prove that $f(x_n) \rightarrow f(x)$. For each $f \in E^*$, we have $|f(x_n) - f(x)| \leq \|f\| \|x_n - x\| \rightarrow 0$. Since $x_n \rightarrow x$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Hence, $f(x_n) \rightarrow f(x)$ for each $f \in E^*$.
- We use the lemma below to prove (c)

Lemma 3.2.5: Let E be a real Banach space and let K be a subset of E . suppose that for each $f \in E^*$, the set $f(K) = \bigcup_{k \in K} f(k)$ is bounded in \mathbb{R} then, K is a bounded subset of E .

Lemma 3.2.6: Let X be a normed linear space, $x \in X$ and X^* denote the dual space of X , then $\|x\| = \sup\{|f(x)|: f \in X^*, \|f\| = 1\}$.

Coming back to the main proof, it suffices to prove that for each $f \in E^*$, $\{f(x_n)\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is bounded. Since $x_n \rightarrow x$ we have from (a) above that for each $f \in E^*$ that $f(x_n) \rightarrow f(x)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Hence $\{f(x_n)\}$ is bounded for each $f \in E^*$ and thus by the lemma 2 above, it follows that $\{x_n\}$ is bounded. Now, since $f \in E^*$ we have $|f(x_n)| \leq \|f\| \|x_n\|$. Taking the *lim inf* of both sides as $n \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain $|f(x_n)| \leq \|f\| \lim inf \|x_n\|$. By lemma 3 above, taking the *sup* over all $f \in E^*$, $\|f\| = 1$.

We have $\sup_{\|f\|=1, f \in E^*} |f(x_n)| \leq \sup_{\|f\|=1, f \in E^*} (\|f\| \lim inf \|x_n\|) \Rightarrow \|x\| \leq \lim inf \|x_n\|$.

d) $|f_n(x_n) - f(x)| \leq |f_n(x_n) - f(x_n)| + |f(x_n) - f(x)| \leq \|f_n - f\| \|x_n\| + |f(x_n) - f(x)|$. Since $x_n \rightarrow x$ we have by (c) that $\exists \alpha > 0$ such that $\|x_n\| \leq \alpha$. From (a) $x_n \rightarrow x \Rightarrow f(x_n) \rightarrow f(x)$. Hence, $|f_n(x_n) - f(x)| \leq \|f_n - f\| \alpha + |f(x_n) - f(x)| \rightarrow 0$. So $f_n(x_n) \rightarrow f(x)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Remark: The above proposition (b) above shows that strong convergence implies that weak convergence. The converse, however is not always true.

Counter Example: Let H be the real Hilbert space and define the sequence $\{e_n\}$ in H by

$e_n = (0, 0, 0, \dots, 0, 1, 0, \dots)$ with 1 in the n th position and zero in every other position.

Proof: we use the Bessel's inequality to prove the counter example.

Lemma 3.2.7 (Bessel's inequality): Let H be a Hilbert space, and suppose that e_1, e_2, \dots is orthonormal sequence in H . Then for any x in H one has $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \langle x, e_k \rangle^2 \leq \|x\|^2$ where $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ denotes the inner product in the Hilbert space H .

Lemma 3.2.8 (Riesz representation theorem): Let H be a Hilbert space and $\varphi \in H^*$ (dual of H), then there exist $f \in H$ such that for any $x \in H$, $\varphi(x) = \langle x, f \rangle$. Moreover $\|f\|_H = \|\varphi\|_{H^*}$

Now to the proof of the counter example.

By Riesz representation theorem, for each $f \in H^*$, $f(e_n) = \langle e_n, z \rangle$ for some unique $z \in H$ and by Bessel's inequality $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |\langle e_n, z \rangle|^2 \leq \|z\|^2$ and so $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |\langle e_n, z \rangle|$ converges. Hence, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \langle e_n, z \rangle = 0$.

But , $f(e_n) = z(e_n) \rightarrow 0$ for each $f \in H^*$. Hence $e_n \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$. However, $\{e_n\}$ does not converge strongly to zero. Since, for $n \neq m$, $\|e_n - e_m\| = \sqrt{2}$ and so $\{e_n\}$ is not convergent.

Proposition 3.2.9: Let $x_0 \in E$; we obtain a neighborhood base at x_0 for the weak topology by considering sets of the form $V = \{x \in E: |f_i(x - x_0)| < \epsilon, i \in J\}$ where J is finite, $f_i \in E^*$ and $\epsilon > 0$.

Proof: we start with the claim that $V = \bigcap_{i \in J} \phi_{f_i}^{-1}(a_i - \epsilon, a_i + \epsilon)$ with $a_i = f_i(x_0)$ is an open set in the weak topology and contain x_0 . The proof of the claim follows easily since

$$\begin{aligned} u \in V &\Leftrightarrow |f_i(u - x_0)| < \epsilon \Leftrightarrow -\epsilon < f_i(u - x_0) < \epsilon \Leftrightarrow -\epsilon < f_i(u) - f_i(x_0) < \epsilon \quad \forall i \in J \\ &\Leftrightarrow a_i - \epsilon < f_i(u) < a_i + \epsilon \Leftrightarrow f_i(u) \in (a_i - \epsilon, a_i + \epsilon) \Leftrightarrow \phi_{f_i}(u) \in (a_i - \epsilon, a_i + \epsilon) \quad \forall i \in J \\ &\Leftrightarrow u \in \bigcap_{i \in J} \phi_{f_i}^{-1}(a_i - \epsilon, a_i + \epsilon) \quad \forall i \in J. \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, $x_0 \in V$ and V is open in the weak topology. Let U be a neighborhood of x_0 for the weak topology. We know there exist a neighborhood U_1 of x_0 . $U_1 \subset V_1$. V_1 is of the form $U_1 = \bigcap_{i \in J} \phi_{f_i}^{-1}(\omega_i)$ where J is finite and ω_i is a neighborhood of $a_i = f_i(x_0)$ in \mathbb{R} . Hence, $\exists \epsilon > 0$ such that $(a_i - \epsilon, a_i + \epsilon) \subset \omega_i$ for each $i \in J$ so that $x_0 \in V \subset V_1 \subset U$.

Proposition 3.2.10: Let E be a finite dimensional normed linear space. Then strong and weak topologies coincide. (In particular, a sequence $\{x_n\}$ in E converges weakly iff it converges strongly).

Proof: Let s and ω denote the strong and weak topology respectively on E . The weak topology always has fewer open sets than the strong topology. So, if a set is open in the weak topology then it is open in the strong topology. hence $\omega \subset s$. Conversely, we must show that a set which is open with respect to the weak topology. Let the dimension of E be n . Let $x_0 \in E$ and U be a neighborhood of x_0 in the strong topology. We shall construct a neighborhood V of x_0 in the weak topology such that $x_0 \in V \subset U$.

In particular, we shall find a set $\{f_i\}_{i \in J}$ with J finite in E^* and $\epsilon > 0$ such that $V = \{x \in E: |f_i(x - x_0)| < \epsilon, i \in J\}$ is contained in U . We now proceed to find $\{f_i\}$ and ϵ . Since U is a neighborhood of x_0 in the strong topology, there exists $r > 0$ such that $B_r(x_0) \subset U$. In fact, we shall construct V such that $x_0 \in V \subset B_r(x_0) \subset U$. We choose a basis $\{e_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ of E with $\|e_i\| = 1 \quad \forall i$. Each $x \in E$ can be written uniquely as $x = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i e_i$.

Define the map $f_i: E \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by $f_i(x) = f_i(\sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i e_i)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Clearly;

- I) f_i is linear for each i .
- II) f_i is bounded for each i

For $|f_i(x)| = |\alpha_i| \leq \max_{1 \leq i \leq n} |\alpha_i| = \|x\|_0 \leq \beta \|x\| \forall x \in E$ for some $\beta > 0$. So $\{f_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n} \in E^*$ and $J = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. We take $\epsilon = \frac{r}{n}$ (where r is radius). We now show with the set $\{f_i\}_{1 \leq i \leq n}$ and this ϵ , the set V defined above is in $B_r(x_0) \subset U$. Let $x_0 = \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i e_i$. Then, for arbitrary $x \in V$, let $x = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i e_i$, then we have: $\|x - x_0\| = \|\sum_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i - \beta_i) e_i\| \leq \sum_{i=1}^n |\alpha_i - \beta_i| \|e_i\| = \sum_{i=1}^n |f_i(x) - f_i(x_0)| = \sum_{i=1}^n |f_i(x - x_0)| < \sum_{i=1}^n \epsilon = r$.

Since $x \in V \Rightarrow |f_i(x - x_0)| < \epsilon$. Hence $x \in B_r(x_0) \subset U$. This complete the proof.

3.3 Open and Closed sets.

Open (respectively Closed) sets in the weak topology are also open (resp. closed) in the strong topology. The converse however, is not always true.

3.3.1 Counter Example:

The set $A = \{x \in E: \|x\| < 1\}$ is clearly open in the strong topology. It is not open in the weak topology. It suffices to prove that A has empty interior. Now suppose for contradiction that $\text{int}(A) \neq \emptyset$. Let $x_0 \in \text{int}(A)$ and U be a neighborhood (in the weak topology) of x_0 . Define $S = \{x \in E: \|x\| = 1\}$ and $h: [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by $h(t) = \|x_0 + ty_0\|$. Notice that:

- I) h is continuous on $[0, \infty)$
- II) $h(0) = \|x_0\| < 1$
- III) $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} h(t) = \infty$

There exist $t_0 > 0$ such that $\|x_0 + t_0 y_0\| = 1$. This implies that $x_0 + t_0 y_0 \in S$. Observe also that if $x := x_0 + t_0 y_0$, then $f_i(x - x_0) = f_i(t_0 y_0) = t_0 f_i(y_0) = 0$ so that $x = x_0 + t_0 y_0 \in U$.

Hence, $x_0 + t_0 y_0 \in S \cap U \subset A \cap U$, a contradiction.

3.4 Weak Topology and Convex Sets.

We have stated above that every closed set in the weak topology is also a closed set in the strong topology i.e., a set which is weakly closed is also strongly closed. In an infinite dimensional space, the converse is false.

Theorem 3.4.1: Let $K \subset E$ be convex and closed (in the strong topology). Then, K is closed in the weak topology, (i.e., if K is strongly closed and convex, then it is weakly closed).

Proof: It suffices to prove that the complement of $K(K^c)$ is open in the weak topology.

Let $x_0 \in K^c$, then $x_0 \notin K$. Since $\{x_0\}$ is convex, non-empty and compact and K is non-empty, convex, closed. It follows from the Hahn Banach theorem that there exist $f \in E^*$, $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $f(x_0) < \alpha < f(x) \forall x \in K$. Set $U = \{x \in E: f(x) < \alpha\}$. Then $x_0 \in U$, $U \cap K = \emptyset$ so that $U \subset K^c$. Moreover, U is open in the weak topology. Hence K^c is open which implies that K is closed in the weak topology.

3.5 The Weak Star Topology.

For each $x \in E$ we consider the map $\phi_x: E^* \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by $\phi_x(f) = f(x)$. As x ranges over E we obtain a family of map $\{\phi_x\}_{x \in E}$ of E^* into \mathbb{R} .

The weak star topology is the smallest topology on E^* for which all the maps ϕ_x are continuous.

We shall ω –topology for the weak topology and ω^* (or *weak** –topology for the weak star topology. The convergence in the weak star topology is denoted by $\xrightarrow{\omega^*}$

Proposition 3.5.1: The *weak** topology is Hausdorff.

Proof: Let E^* be endowed with the weak star topology and f_1, f_2 be arbitrary elements of E^* with $f_1 \neq f_2$. Then there exist $x \in E$ such that $f_1(x) \neq f_2(x)$. Without the loss of generality, let $f_1(x) < f_2(x)$. Introduce $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $f_1(x) < \alpha < f_2(x)$. Set $U_1 = \{f \in E^*: f(x) < \alpha\} = \phi_x^{-1}((-\infty, \alpha))$ and $U_2 = \{f \in E^*: f(x) > \alpha\} = \phi_x^{-1}((\alpha, \infty))$. Then U_1, U_2 are open in the weak star topology, and $f_1 \in U_1$, and $f_2 \in U_2$, $U_1 \cap U_2 = \emptyset$.

Proposition 3.5.2: Let $f_0 \in E^*$; we obtain a neighborhood base at f_0 for the ω^* – topology by considering sets of the form $V = \{f \in E^*: |(f - f_0)(x_i)| < \epsilon, \text{ for all } i \in J\}$ where J is finite, $x_i \in E$ and $\epsilon > 0$.

Proposition 3.5.3: let $\{f_n\}$ be a sequence in E^* . we have the following results.

- a) $f_n \xrightarrow{\omega^*} f \Leftrightarrow f_n(x) \rightarrow f(x)$ for all $x \in E$;
- b) $f_n \rightarrow f \Rightarrow f_n \xrightarrow{\omega^*} f$;
- c) $f_n \xrightarrow{\omega^*} f \Rightarrow \{f_n\}$ is bounded and $\|f\| \leq \liminf \|f_n\|$
- d) $f_n \rightarrow f$ (in E^*), $\Rightarrow f_n \xrightarrow{\omega^*} f$ (in E^*)
- e) $f_n \xrightarrow{\omega^*} f, x_n \rightarrow x \Rightarrow f_n(x_n) \rightarrow f(x)$ in \mathbb{R}

Proof: The proofs follow similar argument of **proposition 3.2.4**

Let X be a real normed space with the dual space X^* and double dual space X^{**}

Remark: If X is reflexive, which is more suitable to apply, then $X^{**} = X$.

In this case, we have

- $f_n, f \in X^*, f_n \rightarrow f$ iff for all $x \in X, f_n(x) \rightarrow f(x)$
- $f_n, f \in X^*, f_n \xrightarrow{\omega^*} f$ iff for all $x \in X, f_n(x) \rightarrow f(x)$

Hence, for reflexive spaces, (weak and *weak** topologies coincide.)

Now let us state without proof the Banach Alaoglu theorem.

Theorem 3.5.4 (Banach Alaoglu theorem): The set $B_{E^*} = \{f \in E^* : \|f\| \leq 1\}$ is compact in the *weak** topology.

3.6 Uniformly Convex Spaces.

Let J be a natural map $J: E \rightarrow E^{**}$ of E into E^{**} defined for each $x \in E$ by $J(x) = \Phi_x(f) \in E^{**}$, where $\Phi_x : E^* \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is given by $\Phi_x(f) = f(x)$ for each $f \in E^*$.

3.6.1 Properties of J

- a. J is linear
- b. $\|Jx\| = \|x\| \forall x \in E$ i.e. J is an isometry. In fact, for each $f \in E^*, \|Jx\| = \sup_{\|f\|, f \in E^*} |J_x(f)| = \sup_{\|f\|, f \in E^*} |f(x)| = \|x\|$.

Proof:

a) J is linear since f is linear

$$J(x + y) = \phi_{x+y}(f) = f(x + y) = f(x) + f(y) = \phi_x(f) + \phi_y(f) = J(x) + J(y)$$

Let k be any scalar

$$J(kx) = \phi_{kx}(f) = f(kx) = kf(x) = k\phi_x(f) = kJ(x).$$

b) $\|Jx\| = \sup_{\|f\|=1} |\phi_x| = \sup_{\|f\|=1} |\phi_x f(x)| = \sup\{|f(x)| : \|f\| = 1\} = \|x\|$ (by lemma 3.2.6)

Definition 3.6.2 (Reflexive Banach Space): Let E be a normed linear space and let J be the canonical map of E into E^{**} . If J is onto, then E is called **reflexive**. Thus, a **reflexive Banach Space** is one in which the canonical map is onto.

Proposition 3.6.3: Let E be a finite dimensional normed linear space. Then the strong, weak and weak star topologies coincide.

Proof: The canonical map J is surjective in the case (since $\dim E = \dim E^* = \dim E^{**}$)

We already know that weak topology is included in the strong topology, we are left to prove the converse. Suppose E is of finite dimension, it has a basis (e_1, \dots, e_n) .

Let $\{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$ be a **basis** of X . If $x \in X$, there exists a unique $(\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_n) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that $x = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i e_i$. Define $\|x\|_\infty = \max_{1 \leq i \leq n} \|\alpha_i\|$. We know that $\|x\|_\infty$ is a norm since all norms in a finite dimensional space are equivalent, the topology given by $\|\cdot\|_\infty$ and $\|\cdot\|$ are the same. Since U is open in the topology given by $\|\cdot\|$, it is open in the topology given by $\|x\|_\infty$. This means that given $x \in U$, there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that $B_\infty(x, \varepsilon) \subset U$, where

$$\begin{aligned} B_\infty(x, \varepsilon) &= \{y \in X : \|x - y\|_\infty < \varepsilon\} \\ &= \{y \in X : |y_i - x_i| < \varepsilon, \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n\} \end{aligned}$$

Note that $U = \bigcup_{x \in U} B_\infty(x, \varepsilon)$

Now, define $f_i: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$) by $f_i(x) = \alpha_i \forall x = \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i e_i$

Then each $f_i \in X^*$ and $B_\infty(x, \varepsilon) = \{y = (y_i) \in X: |f_i(y - x)| < \varepsilon \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n\}$
 $= B(X, f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n, \varepsilon)$

Therefore, U is weakly open.

Similar argument is used to obtain that the weak star topology and the strong topology coincide.

And since both weak and weak star coincides with the strong topology, it follows that the they all coincides. Therefore, the proof is complete.

Remark 3.6.4: In particular, note that E is a reflexive normed linear space if and only if $J(B_\varepsilon) = B_{E^{**}}$

3.7 A Theorem of Kakutani.

Lemma 3.7.1 (Goldstein's Theorem): Let E be a real Banach space then $J(B_\varepsilon)$ is dense in $(B_{E^{**}}, \omega^*)$ where B_ε denote the closed unit ball in E i.e $B_\varepsilon = \{x \in E: \|x\| \leq 1\}$, ω^* denotes the weak star topology and $B_{E^{**}}$ denotes the closed unit ball in E^{**} .

Lemma 3.7.2: Let X and Y be real Banach Spaces and let $T: (X, s) \rightarrow (Y, s)$ be a linear continuous map. Then, $T: (X, \omega) \rightarrow (Y, \omega)$ is continuous and conversely. (Here s denotes the strong topology and ω denotes the weak topology).

We state the proposition without proof

Proposition 3.7.3: Let E be a topology space with the topology τ and let Z be an arbitrary

topology space. Let φ be a mapping of Z into E (i.e $\varphi: Z \rightarrow E$) then φ is continuous if and only if

$\theta_i \circ \varphi$ is continuous from Z onto Y_i , $i \in I$.

Theorem 3.7.4 (Kakutani's Theorem): Let E be a real Banach space. Then E is reflexive iff $B_\epsilon = \{x \in E: \|x\| \leq 1\}$ is weakly compact (i.e iff B_ϵ is compact in the weak topology of E).

Proof: Suppose that E is reflexive, then $J(B_E) = B_{E^{**}}$. Since J^{-1} exists (J is an isometry), this yields $J^{-1}(B_{E^{**}}) = B_E$. By the Banach Alaoglu Theorem, $B_{E^{**}}$ is *weak* compact*. Thus it now suffices to prove that $J^{-1}: (E^{**}, w^*) \rightarrow (E, w)$ is continuous where E^{**} is endowed with *weak** topology and E is endowed with the topology. If this is done, then B_E would be the image of a (*weak**) compact set under a continuous map. This would imply that B_E is compact in the weak topology. We shall use proposition 3.7.3. which will suffice now to prove that for any $f \in E^*$, the map $f \circ J^{-1}: (E^{**}, w^*) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous but, for arbitrary

$$\varphi \in E^{**} \quad (f \circ J^{-1})(\varphi) = f(J^{-1}(\varphi)) = \varphi(f)$$

The last equality follows from $J_x(f) = f(x)$ for each $f \in E^*$. Using the inequality, we conclude that $(f \circ J^{-1})$ is continuous.

The proof is complete. Notice that $f \circ J^{-1}: (E^{**}, w^*) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Since w^* is weak star topology, it follows that $f \circ J^{-1}$ is continuous (by definition of the weak star). Conversely, suppose now B_E is weakly compact. We prove E is reflexive. It suffices to prove $J(B_E) = B_{E^{**}}$. Since

$J: (E, s) \rightarrow (E^{**}, s)$ is an isometry, it is continuous, (here s denotes strong topology). By

Lemma 3.7.2, this implies that $J: (E, w) \rightarrow (E^{**}, w)$ is continuous.

Hence, $J(B_E)$ is w^* -closed in E^{**} . But by Goldstein's Theorem, $J(B_E)$ is dense in $B_{E^{**}}$. Hence, in the w^* -topology of E^{**} , we have $J(B_E) = \overline{J(B_E)} = B_{E^{**}}$. Hence, E is reflexive.

Corollary 3.7.5: Let E be a reflexive real Banach space, K , a closed bounded convex non-empty subset of E . Then K is weakly compact.

Proof: E reflexive $\implies B_E$ is weakly compact by Kakutani's Theorem. k is bounded $\implies k \subset t B_E$

for some $t > 0$. Furthermore, $t B_E$ is weakly compact. k is closed and convex $\implies k$ is weakly

closed by theorem 3.4.1. Hence, k is a weakly closed subset of a weakly compact set, and so k is

weakly compact.

Proposition 3.7.6: Let E be a Reflexive real Banach space and let K be a closed subspace of E . Then K is reflexive.

Corollary 3.7.7: Let E be a real Banach space. Then E is reflexive iff E^* is.

Proof: Let E be reflexive, we prove that E^* is reflexive. By kakutani's theorem, it suffices to

prove that B_{E^*} is compact in the weak topology of E^* . By Banach Alaoglu Theorem, B_{E^*} is

compact in weak star topology of E^* . Since E is reflexive, the weak star topology of E^* = the

weak topology of E^* . Hence, B_{E^*} is compact in the weak topology of E^* . By Kakutani's theorem,

E^* is reflexive.

Conversely, let E^* be reflexive, we want to prove that E is reflexive. By the first part, we know

that E^{**} is reflexive. But $J(E)$ is closed subspace of E^{**} and hence by proposition 3.7.6, $J(E)$ is

reflexive. Since J is an isometry, E is reflexive.

Lemma 3.7.8 (Helly's Theorem): Let E be a real Banach space. $\{f_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}} \in E^*$ and $\{\alpha_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}} \in \mathbb{R}$ fixed, then the following are equivalent:

- I. $\forall \epsilon > 0 \exists x_\epsilon \in E$ such that $\|x_\epsilon\| \leq 1$ and $|f_i(x_\epsilon) - \alpha_i| < \epsilon \forall i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$.
- II. $|\sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \alpha_i| \leq \|\sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i f_i\| \forall \beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_n \in \mathbb{R}$.

Theorem 3.7.9 (Eberlein – Smul'yan Theorem): A real Banach Space E is reflexive iff every (norm) bounded sequence in E has a subsequence which converges weakly to an element of E .

3.8 Uniformly Convex Spaces (cont'd).

Let E be a real Banach space, and $B_r(x_0)$ and $S_r(x_0)$ denote the open Sphere and the ball, respectively, centered at x_0 and with radius $r > 0$. i.e

$$B_r(x_0) = \{x \in E : \|x - x_0\| = r\}$$

$$S_r(x_0) = \{x \in E : \|x - x_0\| < r\}$$

Definition 3.8.1: A Banach space E is called uniformly convex if for any $\epsilon \in (0, 1]$, there exist a $\delta = \delta(\epsilon) > 0$ such that if $x, y \in E$ with $\|x\| \leq 1, \|y\| \leq 1$ and $\|x - y\| \geq \epsilon$, then $\left\| \frac{1}{2}(x + y) \right\| \leq 1 - \delta$.

Theorem 3.8.2: Every real inner product space H is uniformly convex.

Theorem 3.8.3: The l_p space, $1 < p < \infty$ is uniformly convex.

Lemma 3.8.3 (R. C. James): Let $E = l_p$. Then for $p, q > 1$ such that $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ and for each pair $x, y \in E$, the following inequalities hold:

- I. $\left\| \frac{1}{2}(x + y) \right\|^q + \left\| \frac{1}{2}(x - y) \right\|^q \leq [2^{-1}(\|x\|^p + \|y\|^p)]^{q-1}$ for $1 < p \leq 2$, and
- II. $\|x + y\|^p + \|x - y\|^p \leq 2^{p-1}(\|x\|^p + \|y\|^p)$ for $2 \leq p < \infty$.

The following are not uniformly convex.

- I. The space l_1

Counter Example:

Take $\epsilon = 1$ and choose $x = (1,0,0, \dots), y = (0, -1,0,0, \dots)$. Clearly $x, y \in l_1$ and $\|x\|_{l_1} = 1 = \|y\|_{l_1}, \|x - y\|_{l_1} = 2 > \epsilon$. However $\left\| \frac{1}{2}(x + y) \right\| = 1$ so that $\left\| \frac{1}{2}(x + y) \right\| \leq 1 - \delta, \delta > 0$ is not satisfied, showing that l_1 is not uniformly convex.

II. The space l_∞

Counter Example:

Consider $x = (1,1,0,0, \dots), y = (-1,1,0,0, \dots)$ and take $\epsilon = 1$ then, $\|x\|_{l_\infty} = \|y\|_{l_\infty} = 1, \|x - y\|_{l_\infty} = 2 > \epsilon$. However, $\left\| \frac{1}{2}(x + y) \right\|_{l_\infty} = 1$, and so l_∞ is not uniformly convex.

III. The space $C[a, b]$ of all real-valued continuous function on the compact interval $[a, b]$ endowed with the ‘‘Sup norm’’ is not uniformly convex.

Counter Example:

Choose two functions f and g as follows

$$f(t) = 1 \forall t \in [a, b]$$

$$g(t) = \frac{b - t}{b - a} \text{ for each } t \in [a, b]$$

Take $\epsilon = \frac{1}{2}$ clearly, $f, g \in C[a, b], \|f\| = \|g\| = 1$ and $\|f - g\| = 1 > \epsilon$. Also $\left\| \frac{1}{2}(f + g) \right\| = 1$ and so $C[a, b]$ is not uniformly convex.

Theorem 3.8.4 (Milman-Pettis Theorem): Every Uniformly Convex real Banach space E is reflexive.

3.9 Separable spaces.

A metric space is called **Separable** if it contains a countable dense subset i.e iff there is a countable set $S, S \subset E$ such that $\bar{S} = E$

Theorem 3.9.1: Let E be a real normed linear space such that E^* is separable. Then E is separable.

Remark 3.9.2: The converse of the above theorem is not true.

Counter Example: l_1 is separable but $l_1^* = l_\infty$ is not.

Theorem 3.9.2: A real Banach space E is reflexive and Seperable iff E^* is reflexive and separable.

Theorem 3.9.3: Let E be a reflexive real Banach space, then for each $f^* \in E^*$ there exists some $x_0 \in E$, with $\|x_0\| = 1$ such that $f^*(x_0) = \|f^*\|$. The converse is also true.

CHAPTER FOUR

CONVEX OPTIMIZATION IN BANACH SPACES

We start by stating the following theorems.

Theorem 4.0.1: Let $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuous, then there $x^* \in [a, b]$ such that $f(x^*) = \min_{x \in [a, b]} f(x)$.

Theorem 4.0.2: Let $E = \mathbb{R}^N$, $N \in \mathbb{N}$ and $K \subset E$ be compact. Let $f: K \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuous, then there exists $x^* \in K$ such that $f(x^*) = \min_{x \in K} f(x)$.

Theorem 4.0.3: Let X be a reflexive real Banach space and K be a closed convex bounded and non-empty subset of X . Let $f: K \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ be lower semi-continuous and convex, then $\tilde{x} \in K$ such that $f(\tilde{x}) \leq f(x) \forall x \in K$ i.e. $f(\tilde{x}) = \inf_{x \in K} f(x) = \min_{x \in K} f(x)$.

Theorem 4.0.4: Let X be a reflexive real Banach space and $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ be a convex proper lower semi-continuous function. Suppose $\lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow \infty} f(x) = +\infty$, then there exist $\tilde{x} \in X$ such that $f(\tilde{x}) \leq f(x) \forall x \in X$ i.e. $f(\tilde{x}) = \inf_{x \in X} f(x)$.

4.1 Convexity and Semi-Continuity.

Definition 4.1.1 (Convex Set): Let X be a Real linear space and $A \subset X$. The set A is called **Convex** if for each $x_1, x_2 \in A$ and for each $t \in [0, 1]$, we have $tx_1 + (1 - t)x_2 \in A$.

Diagram of a Convex Set.

For example, Consider the set of closed unit sphere denoted by $S_1(x)$ and defined by $S_1(x) = \{x: \|x\| \leq 1\}$, then $S_1(x)$ is a convex set

Proof: let $x, y \in S_1(x)$. hence $\|x\| \leq 1, \|y\| \leq 1$ and $t \in [0,1]$.

so $\|tx + (1 - t)y\| \leq |t|\|x\| + |1 - t|\|y\| \leq |t| + |1 - t| \leq t + 1 - t = 1$.

Thus, $S_1(x)$ is a convex set.

Definition 4.1.2 (Convex Function): Let X be a real vector space and $B \subset X$. Let $f: B \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ be a map. Then f is said to be **convex** if:

b) B is a convex set;

b) $\forall t \in [0,1]$ and for each $x_1, x_2 \in B$, we have

$$f(tx_1 + (1 - t)x_2) \leq tf(x_1) + (1 - t)f(x_2).$$

Remark: if K is a non-empty Convex Set of a linear space X and $f: K \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ is convex, then the extension \hat{f} of the function f to the whole X and by $+\infty$, that is

$$\hat{f}(x) = \begin{cases} f(x) & \text{if } x \in K \\ +\infty & \text{if } x \in X \setminus K \end{cases} \text{ is also convex.}$$

Furthermore, $\inf_K f = \inf_X \hat{f}$.

Graph of a convex function

For example, define $f(x) = |x|$ then f is convex.

Proof: let $t \in [0,1]$ and $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$.

$$\begin{aligned} f(tx + (1-t)y) &= |tx + (1-t)y| \leq |tx| + |(1-t)y| = t|x| + (1-t)|y| \\ &= tf(x) + (1-t)f(y) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, f is convex.

Remark:

iii. f is **concave** if:

a). B is a convex set;

b). $\forall t \in [0,1]$ and for each $x_1, x_2 \in B$, we have

$$f(tx_1 + (1-t)x_2) \geq tf(x_1) + (1-t)f(x_2).$$

iv. f is **proper** if there exists at least one $x_0 \in B$ such that $f(x_0) \neq +\infty$.

Remark: f is convex if and only if $(-f)$ is concave, and vice versa.

Graph of both Convex and Concave Function.

Definition 4.1.3 (Lower Semi-continuous l.s.c): Consider a function $f: \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and a point $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}$.

The function f is said to be lower (resp. upper) semi-continuous at the point x_0 if

$$f(x_0) \leq \liminf_{x \rightarrow x_0} f(x) \quad \left(\text{resp. } f(x_0) \geq \limsup_{x \rightarrow x_0} f(x) \right).$$

The definition can be easily extended to functions defined on subdomains of \mathbb{R} and taking values in the extended real line $[-\infty, \infty]$. If a function is lower (resp. upper) semicontinuous at every point of its domain of definition, then it is simply called a *lower (resp. upper) semi-continuous function*.

Remark: A function f is said to be upper semi-continuous iff $-f$ is lower semi-continuous.

For example, the floor function $f(x) = \lfloor x \rfloor$ which returns the greatest integer less than or equal to a given real number x , is everywhere upper semi-continuous. Similarly, the ceiling function $f(x) = \lceil x \rceil$ is lower semi-continuous.

An upper and a lower semi-continuous function respectively. The solid blue dot indicates $f(x_0)$.

Proposition 4.1.4: f is continuous if and only if it is both upper and lower semi-continuous.

Proof: suppose f is continuous then $\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \inf f(x) = \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \sup f(x) = \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} f(x) = f(x_0)$ for all x_0 .

Therefore, f is both upper and lower semi-continuous.

Conversely, $\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \sup f(x) \leq f(x_0) \leq \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \inf f(x)$. We know that $\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \inf f(x) \leq \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \sup f(x)$.

Therefore, it implies that $\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \sup f(x) = f(x_0) = \lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} \inf f(x)$ and hence $\lim_{x \rightarrow x_0} f(x) = f(x_0)$ for all x_0 and f is continuous.

Proposition 4.1.5: Let X be a normed linear space, $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ of be a map and $U(x_0)$ be the set of all neighborhood x_0 then,

a) For any arbitrary $x_0 \in X$, the following inequality always holds $f(x_0) \geq \sup_{v \in U(x_0)} \inf_{x \in V} f(x)$.

b) f is lower semi-continuous at x_0 if and only if $f(x_0) = \sup_{v \in U(x_0)} \inf_{x \in V} f(x)$.

Definition 4.1.6: A function $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ is lower semi-continuous if it is lower semi-continuous at every point of X .

Proposition 4.1.7: A function $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ is lower semi-continuous if and only if $\forall \lambda \in \mathbb{R}, f^{-1}((\lambda, +\infty])$ is open in X .

Proposition 4.1.8: A function $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ is lower semi-continuous at $x_0 \in X$ if whenever $\{x_n\}$ is a sequence in X such that $x_n \rightarrow x_0$ then,

$$\liminf f(x_n) \geq f(x_0)$$

Theorem 4.1.9: Let $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ be any map. Then, f is convex and lower semi-continuous $\Leftrightarrow f$ is convex and weakly lower semi-continuous.

Corollary 4.1.10: Let $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ be a convex and lower semi-continuous mapping. Suppose $\{x_n\}$ is a sequence in X which converges weakly to \tilde{x} . Then,

$$\liminf f(x_n) \geq f(x_0)$$

Proposition 4.1.11: Let $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ be a map. f is lower semi-continuous if and only if $S_\alpha(f) = \{x \in X : f(x) \leq \alpha\}$ is closed for each $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$

4.2 Coercivity In Reflexive Spaces

Definition 4.2.1: Let X be a topological space. Let K be a subset of X . The set K is said to be **sequentially compact** if every sequence in K has a subsequence which converges to an element of K . the subset K is called **weakly sequentially compact** if every sequence in K has a subsequence which converges weakly to an element of K .

Definition 4.2.2: Let X be a topological space. A function $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ is called (weakly, respectively) sequentially coercive if the closure of every section, $s_\lambda(f) = \{x \in X : f(x) \leq \lambda\}$, is (weakly, respectively) sequentially compact in X .

Definition 4.2.3: Let X be a real reflexive space. A function $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ is called coercive if:

$$\lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow +\infty} f(x) = +\infty$$

Proposition 4.2.4: Let X be a real reflexive space. Then,

$$f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$$

Is weakly sequentially coercive if and only if

$$\lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow +\infty} f(x) = +\infty$$

Remark: if X is reflexive and if

$$\lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow +\infty} f(x) = +\infty$$

We simply say that f is **coercive**.

4.3 Two Fundamental Theorems of Optimization.

Proposition 4.3.1: Let $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ be strictly convex and proper. If f has a minimum at some $x^* \in X$ then x^* is unique.

Proof: Suppose that $a, b \in X$ are such that $a \neq b$ and $f(a) = f(b) = f(x^*) \leq f(x) \forall x \in X$.

$$\text{Then, } f\left(\frac{1}{2}a + \frac{1}{2}b\right) < \frac{1}{2}f(a) + \frac{1}{2}f(b) = f(x^*) = f(a),$$

We arrive at a contradiction. So $a = b$.

Theorem 4.3.2: Let X be a reflexive real Banach space and let K be a closed convex bounded and nonempty subset of X . Let $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ be lower semi-continuous and convex. Then,

$$\exists \tilde{x} \in K \text{ such that } f(\tilde{x}) \leq f(x) \forall x \in K \text{ i. e. } f(\tilde{x}) = \inf_{x \in K} f(x) = \min_{x \in K} f(x).$$

Proof: f is lower semi-continuous and convex $\implies f$ is lower semi-continuous. Put

$$m := \min_{x \in K} f(x)$$

First, Suppose $m = -\infty$. Then for $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\exists x_n \in K$ such that $f(x_n) = -n$.

Boundedness of K implies $\{x_n\}$ is bounded and Eberlein-Smulyan's theorem implies $\exists \{x_{n_k}\}$, subsequence of $\{x_n\}$, such that $x_{n_k} \rightharpoonup x \in X$. But K is convex and closed $\implies K$ is weakly closed.

Hence $x \in K$. By weak lower semi-continuity of f , we have

$$f(x) \leq \liminf f(x_{n_k}) < -\infty$$

And this is impossible (since $c \in \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$). Hence $m \in \mathbb{R}$.

We now use the definition of "inf". Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and take $\epsilon_n = \frac{1}{n}$. Then $\exists x_n \in K$ such that

$$m \leq f(x_n) < m + \frac{1}{n}$$

The sequence $\{x_n\}$ in K implies $\{x_{n_k}\}$ and $\tilde{x} \in K$ such that $x_{n_k} \rightharpoonup \tilde{x}$. Since f is weakly lower semi-continuous, we have

$$f(\tilde{x}) \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} f(x_{n_k}) \leq \liminf_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (m + \frac{1}{n_k}) = \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} (m + \frac{1}{n_k}) = m.$$

Thus, $f(\tilde{x}) \leq m = \inf_{x \in K} f(x)$. But $m \leq f(\tilde{x})$. (Since $m := \min_{x \in K} f(x)$). Hence,

$$f(\tilde{x}) = m = \inf_{x \in K} f(x)$$

Theorem 4.3.3: Let X be a reflexive real Banach space and $f: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ be a convex

proper lower semi-continuous function. Suppose $\lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow \infty} f(x) = +\infty$. Then, $\exists \tilde{x} \in X$ such that

$$f(\tilde{x}) \leq f(x) \forall x \in X \text{ i.e. } f(\tilde{x}) = \inf_{x \in X} f(x).$$

Proof: We shall apply proposition 4.3.1. Since f is proper, $\exists x_0 \in X$ such that $f(x_0) \in \mathbb{R}$, i.e., $f(x_0) \neq +\infty$. Let $K := \{x \in X: f(x) \leq f(x_0)\}$. We now show K is a closed convex, nonempty and bounded set, so that we can apply proposition 4.3.1. But K is a section with $\alpha := f(x_0)$, so it is convex and closed since f is convex and lower semi-continuous (proposition 4.1.11).

Claim: K is bounded. Suppose this is not the case. Then for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\exists x_n \in K$ such that $\|x_n\| > n$. Thus, since $x_n \in K$, we have:

$$f(x_n) \leq f(x_0), \|x_n\| > n.$$

This implies $\lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow \infty} \|x_n\| = +\infty$ and so (by hypothesis), $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n) = +\infty$,

Contradicting the previous inequality. Hence K is bounded. By theorem 4.3.2, it implies

$\exists \tilde{x} \in K \subset X$ such that $\forall x \in K, f(\tilde{x}) \leq f(x)$. Let $x \in X \setminus K$. then $f(x) > f(x_0)$. But $x_0 \in K$. So, $f(\tilde{x}) \leq f(x_0)$. Hence, $f(x) > f(\tilde{x}) \forall x \in X$, i.e., $f(\tilde{x}) \leq f(x) \forall x \in X$.

4.4 Optimization in Real Banach spaces.

Let B be a real reflexive Banach space. We consider the following example of mapping defined on B .

Example 4.4.1 (Projection onto a closed convex subset of B): Let K be a non-empty closed convex subset of B . Let $f: B \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$ be defined for arbitrary $x \in B$ and fixed $u \in B$ by

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} \|x - u\|, & \text{if } x \in K \\ +\infty, & \text{if } x \notin K \end{cases} \text{ then,}$$

- a) f is convex, lower semi-continuous and proper;
- b) $\lim_{\|x\| \rightarrow \infty} f(x) = +\infty$

Thus, there exist $x^* \in K$ such that $f(x^*) = \min_{x \in K} f(x)$.

4.5 Frullani's Integral.

Proposition 4.5.1: Let $f: [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be continuously differentiable function such that $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} f(x) = 0$, and let

$$a, b \in (0, \infty).$$

We

prove

that

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{f(ax) - f(bx)}{x} dx = [f(0) - f(\infty)] \ln\left(\frac{b}{a}\right)$$

Proof:

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{f(ax) - f(bx)}{x} dx = \int_0^{\infty} \left[\frac{f(xt)}{x} \right]_{t=b}^a dx$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \int_0^{\infty} \int_b^a f'(xt) dt dx \\
&= \int_b^a \int_0^{\infty} f'(xt) dx dt \\
&= \int_b^a \left[\frac{f(xt)}{t} \right]_{t=0}^{\infty} dt \\
&= \int_b^a \frac{f(\infty) - f(0)}{t} dt \\
&= (f(\infty) - f(0))(\ln a - \ln b) \\
&= (f(0) - f(\infty)) \ln \left(\frac{b}{a} \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Analysis Justification: we will assume $a < b$. Let $x, y > 0$. We have:

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_x^y \frac{f(at) - f(bt)}{t} dt &= \int_x^y \frac{f(at)}{t} dt - \int_x^y \frac{f(bt)}{t} dt \\
&= \int_{ax}^{ay} \frac{f(u)}{\frac{u}{a}} \frac{du}{a} - \int_{bx}^{by} \frac{f(u)}{\frac{u}{b}} \frac{du}{b} \\
&= \int_{ax}^{ay} \frac{f(u)}{u} du - \int_{bx}^{by} \frac{f(u)}{u} du \\
&= \int_{ax}^{bx} \frac{f(u)}{u} du + \int_{bx}^{ay} \frac{f(u)}{u} du - \int_{bx}^{ay} \frac{f(u)}{u} du - \int_{ay}^{by} \frac{f(u)}{u} du \\
&= \int_{ax}^{bx} \frac{f(u)}{u} du - \int_{ay}^{by} \frac{f(u)}{u} du.
\end{aligned}$$

Since $\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{f(at)-f(bt)}{t} dt = \lim_{y \rightarrow +\infty} \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \int_x^y \frac{f(at)-f(bt)}{t} dt$. If this limit exist, we only have to show that the limits $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \int_{ax}^{bx} \frac{f(u)}{u} du$ and $\lim_{y \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{ay}^{by} \frac{f(u)}{u} du$ exists by computing them.

For the first, we denote $m(x) := \min_{t \in [ax, bx]} f(t)$ and $M(x) := \max_{t \in [ax, bx]} f(t)$.

We have for $x > 0$: $m(x) \ln\left(\frac{b}{a}\right) \leq \int_{ax}^{bx} \frac{f(u)}{u} du \leq M(x) \ln\left(\frac{b}{a}\right)$ and we get

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} m(x) = \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} M(x) = f(0) = 0$$

This is possible because of the continuity of f .

For the second, fix $\epsilon > 0$, we can find x_0 such that if $u \geq x_0$ then $|f(u)| \leq \epsilon$. For $y \geq \frac{x_0}{a}$, we get

$$\left| \int_{ay}^{by} \frac{f(u)}{u} du \right| \leq \epsilon \ln\left(\frac{b}{a}\right).$$

We use the Didier's Remark.

Didier's remark: if f has a limit l at $+\infty$, then $g: x \mapsto f(x) - l$ is continuous and has a limit 0 at $+\infty$.

Then

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \frac{f(at) - f(bt)}{t} dt = \int_0^{+\infty} \frac{g(at) - g(bt)}{t} dt = g(0) \ln\left(\frac{b}{a}\right) = (f(0) - l) \ln\left(\frac{b}{a}\right).$$

Let us now propose an application.

Example 4.5.2: Let X be a reflexive real Banach space and let $S \subset X$ be a convex, compact and non-empty subspace of X . Find the area of the function

$$\frac{\cosh a(x+y) + \cosh b(x+y) + 2 \sinh(ax+by) - \sinh b(x+y) - \sinh a(x+y) - 2 \cosh(ax+by)}{xy}$$

under $K = \{x, y \in S : 0 < x < \infty, 0 < y < \infty\}$.

Solution

To find the area of the function above under K . We just need to integrate the function under K .

$$\text{i.e.} \int_K \frac{\cosh a(x+y) + \cosh b(x+y) + 2 \sinh(ax+by) - \sinh b(x+y) - \sinh a(x+y) - 2 \cosh(ax+by)}{xy}$$

$$= \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\cosh a(x+y) + \cosh b(x+y) + 2 \sinh(ax+by) - \sinh b(x+y) - \sinh a(x+y) - 2 \cosh(ax+by)}{xy} dx dy$$

Simplifying the integrand, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} &= \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-ax-ay} - 2e^{-ax-by} + e^{-bx-by}}{xy} dx dy \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{e^{-ax} - e^{-bx}}{x} \right) \left(\frac{e^{-ay} - e^{-by}}{y} \right) dx dy \\ &= \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-ax} - e^{-bx}}{x} dx \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-ay} - e^{-by}}{y} dy \end{aligned}$$

From proposition 4.5.1, we apply

Here, $f(x) = e^{-x}$, and $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} f(x) = 0$

$f(x)$ is continuously differentiable and $f(0) = 1$, $f(\infty) = \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} f(x) = 0$.

Applying the frullani's integral we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-ax} - e^{-bx}}{x} dx \int_0^{\infty} \frac{e^{-ay} - e^{-by}}{y} dy &= (f(0) - f(\infty))^2 \left[\ln \left(\frac{b}{a} \right) \right]^2 \\ &= (1 - 0)^2 \left[\ln \left(\frac{b}{a} \right) \right]^2 \\ &= \left[\ln \left(\frac{b}{a} \right) \right]^2 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the area of the function is $\left[\ln \left(\frac{b}{a} \right) \right]^2$.

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